
A Descriptive Study of the Pradhan Mantri Development Initiatives for North-East India and Their Impact on Assam.

Dr. Poli Boruah

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics.

L.T.K.College, Azad, North Lakhimpur, Assam.

Email ID : poliboruah11@gmail.com

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 25-02-2025

Published: 14-03-2025

Keywords:

North-East India ,Pradhan Mantri Development Initiative schemes, sustainable development, socio-economic landscape

ABSTRACT

This paper has thrown a light on the descriptive analysis of the Pradhan Mantri Development Initiatives for North-East India, with a particular focus on their effects in Assam. These initiatives aim to tackle the region's unique socio-economic challenges through targeted infrastructure development, social projects, and livelihood opportunities. By examining key schemes like PM-DevINE, the study evaluates their contributions to improving living standards, fostering sustainable development, and diminishing regional disparities. The study collected data from various stakeholders, including government officials and relevant articles, to evaluate the effectiveness and reach of these programs. It aims to assess the impact of the PM-DevINE Scheme in the North-East, examine the socio-economic changes in Assam driven by these initiatives, explore the government's role in implementing the scheme, and identify potential development opportunities in Assam. The findings highlight notable advancements in infrastructure, improved access to services, and increased employment opportunities for youth and women as a result of the PM-DevINE Scheme. However, it also points out ongoing challenges, such as implementation gaps and the necessity for better coordination

among government bodies. Ultimately, this research emphasizes the crucial role of the Pradhan Mantri Development Initiatives in reshaping Assam's socio-economic landscape and provides insights for policymakers to enhance future development strategies in the region.

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15030540>

Introduction:

The PMDevINE, introduced in the 2022-23 Union Budget, is a fully financed Central Sector project with a budget of ₹ 6,600 crore for 2022-26. Its goals are to finance infrastructure in accordance with PM GatiShakti, promote region-specific social projects, generate work opportunities for youth and women, and close developmental gaps in the North East. The policy, which was approved in October 2022, complements existing initiatives by permitting project proposals from federal and state governments.

Impact of PM Devine:

The Prime Minister's Development Initiative for the North Eastern Region (PM-DevINE) was launched as a new Central Sector Scheme in the Union Budget for 2022-23. At the proper time, an impact study of the PM-DevINE scheme will be carried out. According to the scheme's objectives, eleven projects totaling Rs 1,503.44 crore, including seven projects mentioned in the 2022-23 Budget, have been approved for fiscal year 2022-23, as shown in the tables below. Land purchase compensation is managed by the respective State Governments in accordance with applicable laws and regulations because it falls under the jurisdiction of the state. (The time term for sanctioning PM-DevINE scheme projects is 2023-24, followed by completion in 2025-26).

In the financial year 2022-23, 11 projects valued at ₹ 1,503.44 crore were approved, with ₹ 121.10 crore disbursed. The Ministry of Development of North Eastern Region (MDoNER) acts as the coordinating authority, collaborating with state governments, the North Eastern Council, and central ministries for project planning and oversight. The scheme prioritizes sustainable development and livelihood enhancement through a structured project approval process, involving coordination with ministries and NITI Aayog. A key component, PM GatiShakti, strengthens multimodal connectivity and supports

India's economic zones by facilitating integrated infrastructure development (Government of India, Ministry of Development of North East Region Report, 2022).

Review of literature:

Numerous studies have explored various aspects of government development schemes in India. Key works include:

- **Barot (2019)** examined the **Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana (PMAY)**, focusing on its benefits for Economically Weaker Sections (EWS) in Ahmedabad, highlighting issues of urban overcrowding.
- **Khan (2019)** assessed PMAY from a housing adequacy perspective, arguing that addressing housing shortages requires a broader understanding of overall housing needs.
- **Ray (2002)** found the **Swarnjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana (SGSY)** had limited impact on improving beneficiaries' income, identifying a critical threshold below which individuals remain poor.
- **Kareemulla and Ramasundaram (2013)** analyzed the **National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme**, concluding it significantly reduced rural poverty and seasonal labor migration by providing employment for essential expenses.

Although existing studies analyze the effects of central government schemes on India's development, none specifically focus on the role of the Prime Minister's development initiatives in Assam's socio-economic transformation. This research gap serves as the motivation for the present study, which seeks to examine the impact of these initiatives in Assam (Chakraborty,2024).

Objectives:

The present study is based on the following main objectives, these are:

1. To investigate the **impact of the PM-DevINE Scheme in the North Eastern Region.**
2. To analysis **socio-Economic Transformation of Assam through PM Initiatives.**
3. To discuss about the role of Government initiatives in implementing PM-DevINE in Assam.

4. To examine about the potential areas of development under PM-DevINE in Assam:

Methodology:

This study draws on secondary data sources, such as research articles, government reports, websites, journals, books, and other pertinent materials.

Socio-Economic Background of Assam:

Assam, in North-East India, is noted for its diverse landscapes, which include hills, valleys, the Brahmaputra River, and the Kamakhya Temple (Dhar, 2014). The name "Assam" is derived from the Sanskrit word "Asom," which means "unequal" or "unrivalled." It is the largest northeastern state in terms of people and area, encompassing 78,438 square kilometres, or 2.4% of India's total land area (Dhar, 2014). According to the 2011 Census, Assam's population was 31,169,272, with a sex ratio of 954 females per 1,000 males and a female literacy rate of 73.18% (Dhar, 2014).

Most residents live in the fertile valleys of the Brahmaputra and Barak rivers, with **27 districts** in total, including four in the Bodoland Territorial Council (Dhar, 2014). Assam's economy is largely agrarian, with about **61%** of the population engaged in agriculture, supporting over **75%** of the state's populace. However, agricultural growth has been hindered by frequent floods and riverbank erosion (Dhar, 2014).

Assam faces challenges such as geographical isolation, natural disasters, and underdeveloped infrastructure, which impede socio-economic development (Nayak, 2016). Consequently, government initiatives are essential to advance the state's progress (Nayak, 2016).

Impact of the PM-DevINE Scheme in the North Eastern Region:

The Prime Minister's Development Initiative for the North Eastern Region (PM-DevINE) was launched as a new Central Sector Scheme in the Union Budget for 2022-23. At the proper time, an impact study of the PM-DevINE scheme will be carried out. According to the scheme's objectives, eleven projects totaling Rs 1,503.44 crore, including seven projects mentioned in the 2022-23 Budget, have been approved for fiscal year 2022-23, as shown in the tables below. Land purchase compensation is managed by the respective State Governments in accordance with applicable laws and regulations

because it falls under the jurisdiction of the state. (The time term for sanctioning PM-DevINE scheme projects is 2023-24, followed by completion in 2025-26).

State-wise, project wise list of Projects approved during FY 2022-23

Sl	Name of the Project	Project Location(s)/ State	Implementing Agency / Department	Approved Cost (in Rs Crore)
1	Dedicated Services for the Managing Paediatric and Adult Haematolymphoid Cancers in Guwahati ,North East India.	Guwahati - Multi-State.	Dr. B. Borooah Cancer Institute, Guwahati, D/o Atomic Energy.	129
2	NECTAR Livelihood Improvement Project (Multi-State) – Utilising Banana Pseudo Stem for Value-Added Products.(www.studyiq.com)	12 locations in 7 States: Arunachal Pradesh has one, Assam four, Manipur one, Meghalaya one, Mizoram one, Nagalandtwo, Tripura two.	North-East Centre for Technology Application & Research (NECTAR), D/o Science & Technology.	67
3	Promoting Scientific Organic Agriculture in North-East India (Multi-State).	Demo Labs in Meghalaya, Assam and Tripura.	North-East Centre for Technology Application & Research (NECTAR), D/o Science & Technology.(www.studyiq.com)	45
4	Gap funding for Passenger Ropeway System from	West Sikkim-Sikkim.(www.studyiq.com)	Tourism and Civil Aviation Department, Govt. of	64

	Pelling to Sanga-Choeling in West Sikkim - at the cost of Rs. 63.39 Crore (58%) of total cost of Rs.108.39 Crore.(www.studyiq.com)		Sikkim.(www.studyiq.com)	
5	Gap funding for Eco-friendly Passenger Ropeway (Cable Car) from Dhapper to Bhaleydunga in South Sikkim - at the cost of Rs. 57.82 Crore (28%) of total cost of Rs. 209.57 Crore.(www.studyiq.com)	South Sikkim- Sikkim.(www.studyiq.com)	Tourism and Civil Aviation Department, Govt. of Sikkim.(www.studyiq.com)	58
6	Construction of Aizwal By-pass road on Western Side.(www.studyiq.com)	45 km from NH-108 at Sinhmui to Aizwal–Lunglei Road, Mizoram.(www.studyiq.com)	Public Works Department, Govt. of Mizoram.(www.studyiq.com)	500
7	Pilot project for the construction of Bamboo Link Roads at different locations in various districts in the State of Mizoram - (i) Tuirial Airfield to North Chaltlang (18 km) at a cost of Rs. 33.58 Crore; and (ii)	Tuirial Airfield to North Chaltlang; and Lengpui to Saiphai, Mizoram.(www.studyiq.com)	Public Works Department, Govt. of Mizoram.(www.studyiq.com)	100

	Lengpui to Saiphai Bamboo Plantation (41 km) at a cost of Rs. 66.42 crore.(www.studyiq.com)			
8	Construction of new four-lane road and conversion of existing two-lane road into four-lane with cycling tracks, utility ducts, footpaths, etc. at New Shillong Township.(www.studyiq.com)	New Shillong, Meghalaya.(www.studyiq.com)	Directorate of Urban Affairs, Govt. of Meghalaya.(www.studyiq.com)	146.79
9	Transformation of 20 schools as Centre of Excellence in the Kamrup District.(www.studyiq.com)	Kamrup District, Assam.(www.studyiq.com)	Public Works Department, Govt. of Assam.(www.studyiq.com)	132.86
10	Establishment of Solar Micro Grid for supply of reliable power to Remote Habitations in Tripura.(www.studyiq.com)	274 Remote hamlets across Tripura State.(www.studyiq.com)	TREDA, Department of Power, Govt. of Tripura.(www.studyiq.com)	80.79
11	Livelihood projects relating to Special Development of Eastern Nagaland - (22 Nos.)	4 Districts of Nagaland.(www.studyiq.com)	Department of Under Developed Areas (DUDA), Govt. of Nagaland.(www.studyiq.com)	180

	.(www.studyiq.com)		m)	
--	--------------------	--	----	--

(Source :This information was given by Union Minister for Ministry of Development of North Eastern Region, **Shri G. Kishan Reddy** in a written reply in Lok Sabha on 24th July 2023).

Prime Minister's Development Initiative for North East Region (PM-DevINE):

The total approved outlay for PM-DevINE scheme for the period from 2022-23 to 2025-26 is Rs.6600 crore (Reddy,2023). Under the Scheme, projects are posed by the respective State Governments and Other Agencies based on felt needs of the NE States/ NER. Details of the projects sanctioned (AFS issued), recommended for sanction and recommended in-principle (selected) under the Scheme against the approved outlay of the scheme are given at Table-A, Table-B and Table-C respectively (Reddy,2023).

At this juncture, the approved expenditure outlay of Rs.6600 crore for the scheme is considered adequate to meet the fund requirements of the projects taken up under the scheme(Reddy,2023).

This information was given by the Union Minister of Development of North Eastern Region Shri G Kishan Reddy in a written reply to a question in Rajya Sabha on 07 DEC 2023.

Table-A

Details of the projects sanctioned under PM-DevINE:

Sl.	Name of the Project	State Agency	Implementing Department / Agency	Approved Cost as per AFS (in • cr.)	PM-DevINE Sector	Functional Sector
1	Transformation of 20 schools as Centre of Excellence in the Kamrup District	Assam	PWD	132.86	Social Development	Education
2	Pilot project for the	Mizoram	PWD	100.00	Infrastructure	Roads

	construction of Bamboo Link Roads at different locations in various districts in the State of Mizoram - (i) Tuirial Airfield to North Chaltlang (18 km) at a cost of Rs. 33.58 Crore; and (ii) Lengpui to Saiphai Bamboo Plantation (41 km) at a cost of Rs. 66.42 crore					
3	Livelihood projects relating to Special Development of Eastern Nagaland - (22 Nos.)	Nagaland	DUDA	180.00	Social Development	Agriculture & Allied, Tourism, Livelihood
4	Gap funding for Passenger Ropeway System from Pelling to Sanga-Choeling in West Sikkim - <i>at the cost of Rs. 63.39 Crore (58%) of total cost of Rs.108.39 Crore</i>	Sikkim	Tourism and Civil Aviation	63.39	Infrastructure	Tourism
5	Gap funding for	Sikkim	Tourism and	57.82	Infrastructure	Tourism

	Eco-friendly Passenger Ropeway (Cable Car) from Dhapper to Bhaleydunga in South Sikkim - <i>at the cost of Rs. 57.82 Crore (28%) of total cost of Rs. 209.57 Crore</i>		Civil Aviation			
6	Establishment of Solar Micro Grid for supply of reliable power to Remote Habitations in Tripura	Tripura	TREDA, D/o Power	80.79	Social Development	Power
7	Establishment of Dedicated Services for the Management of Paediatric and Adult Haematolymphoid Cancers in North East India, Guwahati	Central/Other Agency	Dr. BBCI Guwahati (DAE, GoI)	129.00	Social Development	Health
8	NECTAR Livelihood Improvement Project (Multi-State)	Central/Other Agency	NECTAR (DST, GoI)	67.00	Livelihood	Agriculture

	- Utilization of Banana Pseudo Stem for Value-Added Products					
9	Promoting Scientific Organic Agriculture in North-East India (Multi-State)	Central/Other Agency	NECTAR (DST, GoI)	44.99	Livelihood	Agriculture
	Total 9 projects			855.85		

(Source: Ministry of Development of North-East Region. Posted On: 07 DEC 2023)

Table-B:

Details of the projects recommended for sanction under PM-DevINE:

Sl.	Title of the Project	State / Project Proposer	Implementing Department / Agency	Proposed Cost (• Crore)	PM-DevINE Sector	Functional Sector(s)
1	Construction Of Medical College (100 Admissions) at Sivasagar District, Assam	Assam	PWD	500.00	Social Development	Health
2	Upgradation/widening of existing 2 lane road to 4 lane road connecting LGB International Airport – From VIP	Assam	PWD	269.75	Infrastructure	Roads

	junction to Dharapur Junction					
3	Development of Maa Kamakhya Access Corridor at Guwahati in the Capital region.	Assam	PWD	499.89	Infrastructure	Tourism
Total 3 projects				1269.64		

(Source: Ministry of Development of North-East Region. Posted On: 07 DEC 2023)

Table-C:

Details of the projects recommended in principle (selected) under PM-DevINE:

Sl.	Title of the Project	State / Project Proposer	Implementing Department / Agency	Proposed Cost	PM-DevINE Sector	Functional Sector(s)
				(• Crore)		
1	Construction of new four-lane road and conversion of existing two-lane road into four-lane with cycling tracks, utility ducts, footpaths, etc. at New Shillong Township	Meghalaya	Dte. of Urban Affairs	146.79	Infrastructure	Urban Development
2	Construction of	Mizoram	PWD	500	Infrastructure	Urban

	Aizawl By-pass road on Western Side					Development
3	Construction of Advance Landing Ground (ALG) at Anini and Dirang	Arunachal Pradesh	PWD	408.42	Infrastructure	Aviation
4	Development of Infrastructure of the Processing Zone of Manipur IT SEZ at Mantripukhri, Imphal	Manipur	IT Dept.	120	Infrastructure	IT / ITeS
5	Development of Infrastructure for Manipur Technical University (MTU), Imphal West District	Manipur	MTU	55.04	Social Development	Higher Education
6	Construction and Equipping of 60 Bedded State Mental Hospital in Manipur	Manipur	Health	70.47	Social Development	Health
7	Construction of IT Park at Tura, West Garo Hills District	Meghalaya	IT & Comm.	100	Infrastructure	ITeS

8	Construction of 220/132 kV (2x100 MVA) & 132/33 kV (2x50 MVA) Sub-station at Tsitrongse-Dimapur with associated lines	Nagaland	Power	132.37	Infrastructure	Power
9	100 Bedded Hospital at district HQ, Peren	Nagaland	Health & Family W	50	Social Development	Health
10	Multi-speciality hospital in Chumokedemia	Nagaland	Health & Family W	60	Social Development	Health
11	Upgradation of the Radiation Oncology Centre at CIHSR	Nagaland	Health & Family W	58.5	Social Development	Health
12	Infrastructure Development of Polytechnics in Nagaland	Nagaland	Technical Edu.	30	Social Development	Higher Education
13	Skywalk Project at Bhaleydhunga, Yangang in South Sikkim	Sikkim	Tourism & Civil Aviation	220	Social Development	Tourism
14	Construction of	Sikkim	Tourism &	*200.29	Social	Tourism

	Gyan Mandir Library at Gangtok.		Civil Aviation			Development	
15	Conversion of Singshore Bridge as a glass skywalk bridge for tourist attraction in West Sikkim	Sikkim	Tourism & Civil Aviation	52		Social Development	Tourism
16	Establishment of Dental College at Agartala	Tripura	Health & Family W	202		Social Development	Health
17	Establishment of 200 bedded MCH (Maternal & Child Health) wing at AGMC & GBP Hospital	Tripura	Health & Family W	192		Social Development	Health
*Subject to cost optimization at DPR Stage							
18	Setting up of Integrated Rehabilitation Centre for drug addicted.	Tripura	Health & Family W	121.9		Social Development	Health
19	Proposal to set up a Digital Design and 3D Printing	Other Agencies	NEC / AMTRON	54.9		Livelihood	Skilling/ Entrepreneurship

	Centre of Excellence in the Electronic Mfg. Cluster (EMC) in collaboration with other Govt Agencies to be located at Tech City, Guwahati					
20	Establishment of State Level Innovation Hub in North Eastern states for Entrepreneurship development & startup technology development programme.	z-Other Agencies	O/o PSA to GoI	102.93	Livelihood	Skilling/ Entrepreneurship
21	Proposal for development of Entrepreneurial & Startup Ecosystem of NER	Other Agencies	EDII, Ahmedabad / NEC	46.65	Livelihood	Skilling/ Entrepreneurship
22	To establish an Artist's Village for promotion of world's most unique Pottery Art	Other Agencies	NEC	-	Livelihood	Handicraft

	from Longpi Black Pottery of Manipur					
	22 Projects			2,924.26		

(Source: Ministry of Development of North-East Region. Posted On: 07 DEC 2023)

Socio-Economic Transformation of Assam through PM Initiatives:

The Government of Assam proactively adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) before the UN officially endorsed the 2030 Agenda, launching the Single Synergized Initiative (SSI) to promote future-ready governance. This initiative engages citizens, forms new partnerships, and introduces innovative projects, following a "whole of government" strategy to ensure collaboration across all departments. It replaces the previous planning framework led by the Planning Commission and the State Planning Board. Additionally, Pradhan Mantri schemes have significantly contributed to Assam’s socio-economic development by addressing issues like poverty, infrastructure gaps, and unemployment (Government of Assam, 2017).

1.Rural Development and Poverty Alleviation:

Amidst the COVID-19 pandemic, the Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana-Urban (PMAY-U) in Assam prioritized shelter, food, and essential care for vulnerable groups such as EWS families, laborers, the homeless, daily wage earners, and urban poor. In response to the pandemic, the State Mission Directorate of PMAY-U developed a plan to support construction workers, migrant laborers, and suppliers by ensuring 100% grounding of Beneficiary Led Construction (BLC) houses in all urban areas(Government of Assam,2020). The initiative "Griha Adharxila 2020, Assam" aimed to provide permanent homes with kitchens and toilets to EWS families. A "Griha Pravesh" ceremony was held in January 2020 to distribute the final installment to beneficiaries, and a similar event, "Griha Xilanyash 2020," was inaugurated in July 2020. Additionally, the Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY) significantly improved rural infrastructure and connectivity across Assam(Government of Assam,2020).

Some key aspects of PMGSY's performance in Assam include:

1. **Enhanced Rural Connectivity:** The PMGSY has significantly improved road connectivity in remote and rural regions, linking towns and villages that were previously isolated with crucial services like healthcare, education, and market access. This has positively transformed the socio-economic landscape of rural communities.
2. **Achievement of Road Construction Goals:** Assam has made remarkable strides in fulfilling its road construction objectives under the PMGSY, leading to the development of thousands of kilometers of all-weather roads that ensure reliable access for numerous rural households.
3. **Connecting Unserved Villages:** A primary goal of PMGSY in Assam has been to connect unserved areas. As a result, many villages have gained access to the road network for the first time, which has helped lessen rural isolation and foster economic development.
4. **Emphasis on Quality Control and Monitoring:** The state has prioritized the quality control and monitoring of roads built under PMGSY, ensuring these infrastructures meet established standards and remain sustainable over time.
5. **Economic and Employment Impact:** The execution of PMGSY has created significant job opportunities, especially in rural regions. Additionally, it has stimulated local economies by enhancing access to markets and easing the transport of goods.

Despite these successes, challenges like difficult terrain, adverse weather conditions, and limited resources occasionally hinder the timely completion of projects. However, PMGSY's overall impact in Assam has been positive, significantly contributing to rural development and poverty reduction (Government of Assam, 2020)

2. Employment Generation and Skill Development :

The Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) has been in place in Assam since 2016, with the primary purpose of extending crop insurance coverage in the state. The system offers farmers insurance cover and financial support in the event of crop failure caused by natural catastrophes, pests, or disease. It also seeks to stabilise farmers' earnings, allowing them to continue farming despite potential

losses.

In Assam, farmers planting recognised crops on up to 1 hectare of land can receive insurance for about
• 1 thanks to government subsidies (Government of Assam, Department of Agriculture and Horticulture).

Under the initiative, the government has notified Black Gramme, Sali Paddy, and Jute for the Kharif season, as well as Summer Paddy, Potato, Sugarcane, Rape & Mustard for the Rabi season. The scheme is implemented at the Gaon Panchayat (GP) level as the Unit of Insurance for all districts, with the exception of those in the Bodoland Territorial Region (BTR), Karbi Anglong Autonomous Council (KAAC), and North Cachar Hills Autonomous Council (NCHAC), where the Block serves as the Insurance Unit.

From Rabi 2021-22, five insurance companies were empaneled for the next three years to implement the scheme. Assam's 33 districts have been divided into eight clusters, with each cluster assigned to an insurance company (Government of Assam, Department of Agriculture and Horticulture).

Cluster and District-wise Insurance Companies:

(According to Government of Assam, Department of Agriculture and Horticulture report).

1. **Agriculture Insurance Company of India Ltd.:** Kamrup (R), Kokrajhar, Goalpara, Dima Hasao
2. **Reliance General Insurance Company Ltd.:** Jorhat, Majuli, Golaghat, Nalbari, Karbi Anglong, West Karbi Anglong
3. **SBI General Insurance Company Ltd.:** Barpeta, Karimganj, Sivasagar, Charaideo
4. **Agriculture Insurance Company of India Ltd.:** Bongaigaon, Sonitpur, Biswanath, Dhemaji
5. **Agriculture Insurance Company of India Ltd.:** Dhubri, South Salmara, Darrang, Hailakandi
6. **HDFC Ergo General Insurance Company Ltd.:** Udalguri, Tinsukia, Lakhimpur, Cachar
7. **Future Generali India Insurance Company Ltd.:** Nagaon, Hojai, Chirang, Dibrugarh
8. **Agriculture Insurance Company of India Ltd.:** Kamrup (M), Morigaon, Baksa

The Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY):

Launched in 2015, the Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) aims to enhance skill development by providing free training and financial incentives for skill certification, improving the

employability of young individuals. PMKVY 2.0 (2016-2020) expanded into additional sectors and aligned with initiatives such as "Make in India" and "Digital India." PMKVY 3.0 (2020-2021) focused on fostering an ecosystem for informed career decisions, skill certification, and greater private sector participation, with the objective of benefiting 8 lakh youth (Government of India, 2020).

In Assam, PMKVY has been instrumental in promoting skill development and empowering youth. It targets sectors with high employment potential like construction, agriculture, retail, hospitality, and healthcare. Accredited training centres provide courses ranging from soft skills to technical trades. The scheme prioritizes marginalized groups, including women and economically disadvantaged individuals, and offers placement and entrepreneurship support. Partnerships with local industries ensure skills match market needs, while region-specific skills like weaving and agriculture support Assam's cultural and economic landscape. PMKVY has been crucial in addressing unemployment and fostering skill development in the state (Government of India 2020).

3. Women Empowerment:

India's development has been closely tied to women's empowerment, with the government prioritizing numerous initiatives over the past nine years. Key achievements include the passage of the Nari Shakti Vandan Adhiniyam, granting 33% reservation for women in legislative bodies, and improving the national sex ratio to 1020 females per 1000 males. Other significant milestones include extending paid maternity leave to 26 weeks, opening 3.2 crore Sukanya Samruddhi Yojana accounts, and providing nearly 10 crore LPG gas cylinders under the PM Ujjwala Yojana. Additionally, 72% of homes under the PM Awas Yojana Gramin are owned by women, and maternal mortality has fallen to 97 deaths per lakh live births (Ministry of Information & Broadcasting, Government of India, 2024).

Initiatives like abolishing Triple Talaq and financial programs like PMMY and Stand-Up India have supported women entrepreneurs, with women receiving 69% of loans under PMMY and 84% under Stand-Up India. Women now also have permanent commissions in 12 Arms and Services, and India has the highest percentage of female STEM graduates globally at 43% (Ministry of Information & Broadcasting, Government of India, 2024).

Programs like Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao (BBBP) have improved gender parity, with the sex ratio at birth rising from 918 to 937. POSHAN Abhiyaan and the extension of maternity leave support motherhood,

while the PM Awas Yojana and PM Ujjwala Yojana enhance women's financial inclusion and health.(Ministry of Information & Broadcasting,Government of India,2024).

In Assam, the government has embraced women-led development, with initiatives that empower women economically, socially, and politically, ensuring their active role in shaping the state's progress (Ministry of Information & Broadcasting,Government of India,2024).

Key initiatives empowering women in Assam include:

1.Mahila Shakti Kendra (MSK):Centers on ability advancement, work, computerized proficiency, and get to to government plans, empowering ladies to require administration parts in provincial ranges.

2. Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (BBBP):Has moved forward sex proportion and female proficiency, advancing the esteem of the young lady child and guaranteeing their instruction.

3.Self-Help Bunches (SHGs) and Ladies Business enterprise:
Women-led SHGs, backed by the National Country Employments Mission (NRLM), are driving financial development in agribusiness, handloom, and creates.

4.Assam State Commission for Ladies:
Addresses gender-based viciousness, lawful rights, and sex correspondence, guaranteeing women's get to to equity.

5.Women's Representation in Nearby Administration:
Expanded women's interest in decision-making in Panchayati Raj Educate and regions.

6.Farming and Country Economy:
Ladies get preparing, assets, and money related back to lead rural wanders.

7.Back for Ladies Artisans and Handloom Laborers:
Government plans offer assistance ladies artisans turn their abilities into feasible businesses.

8.Social Welfare and Wellbeing Activities:
Programs like Poshan Abhiyaan and PM Matritva Vandana Yojana back women's wellbeing and diminish maternal mortality.

9.Instruction and Expertise Advancement:
Centers on making strides girls' enrollment in schools and professional preparing, with activities

promoting digital education and financial interest.

Assam's move from ladies improvement to women-led advancement is realized through focused on programs that engage ladies in wellbeing, instruction, monetary incorporation, and authority, situating them as key supporters to the state's advance.

4. Infrastructure Development:

The Pradhan Mantri development initiatives have profoundly altered Assam's socioeconomic landscape, particularly through programs like the Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY), which increased rural road connectivity by sanctioning 1,574.97 km of roads with a budget of ₹ 304.92 million. The North East Special Infrastructure Development Scheme (NESIDS) revised in 2022 focuses on gap-funding for road and non-road infrastructure projects, with ₹ 18,488.94 crore granted to 1,548 projects, 1,098 of which have been completed (Ministry of Rural Development, Government of India).

The North Eastern Council (NEC) schemes aim to bridge development gaps across various sectors, with a budget allocation of ₹ 1,778.76 crore for new projects. Special development packages for the Bodoland Territorial Council (BTC), Karbi Anglong Autonomous Territorial Council (KAATC), and Dima Hasao Autonomous Territorial Council (DHATC) have made substantial progress, with funds dedicated to infrastructure projects resulting in numerous completed and ongoing developments (Ministry of Development of North-East Region, 2023).

These initiatives have focused on critical areas like housing, infrastructure, financial inclusion, agriculture, and skill development, contributing to poverty reduction, employment generation, and better living standards in Assam. While challenges remain due to geographical isolation and natural disasters, the overall impact of these schemes has been transformative, helping Assam integrate into national development. Moving forward, efforts should focus on addressing implementation gaps, expanding scheme coverage, and ensuring inclusivity for marginalized groups (Ministry of Development of North-East Region, 2023).

Importance of Government Initiatives:

The success of the **PM-DevINE scheme** in Assam hinges on well-coordinated government initiatives at both the state and central levels. Key areas include:

1. **Strategic Planning and Policy Formulation:** Government initiatives are essential for addressing Assam's unique challenges like floods and underdeveloped infrastructure. Policies should focus on flood management, connectivity, healthcare, and education to address socio-economic gaps.
2. **State-Central Government Coordination:** Effective collaboration between Assam and the central government ensures seamless implementation, proper fund allocation, and timely project completion. Regular reviews and data-sharing are necessary for smooth operations.
3. **Infrastructure Development:** Building roads, bridges, healthcare facilities, and flood-resistant infrastructure is key to improving connectivity, access to services, and boosting local economies.
4. **Financial Allocation and Resource Mobilization:** Proper fund allocation and transparent utilization are critical to project success. Monitoring systems ensure efficient use of resources, accelerating development.
5. **Capacity Building and Skill Development:** Local manpower is essential for large-scale projects. Skill development programs should align with project needs, generating local employment and reducing dependency on external labor.
6. **Public-Private Partnerships (PPP):** The government should facilitate private-sector investments in infrastructure, tourism, agriculture, and healthcare, providing tax incentives and simplified regulations to accelerate development.
7. **Monitoring, Evaluation, and Transparency:** Strong monitoring systems using digital tools ensure transparency, reduce corruption, and keep projects on time and within budget.

These initiatives collectively aim to transform Assam's socio-economic landscape through efficient execution, financial transparency, and public-private collaboration

Potential Areas of Development Under PM-DevINE in Assam:

Government initiatives under **PM-DevINE** in Assam can target the following key areas for socio-economic development:

1. **Flood and Disaster Management:** Assam's frequent floods cause economic losses and damage. The government should implement flood management projects like embankments and early warning systems to protect livelihoods and infrastructure.
2. **Agricultural Modernization:** With agriculture being central to Assam's economy, the government can promote modern farming, improve credit access, and strengthen supply chains, boosting farmer incomes and reducing poverty.
3. **Tourism Development:** Assam has potential for eco and cultural tourism but lacks infrastructure. Investments in road connectivity and promotion of cultural heritage can create jobs and increase revenue.
4. **Healthcare and Education:** Assam's rural areas need better access to healthcare and education. Government efforts to build and upgrade facilities will improve quality of life, human capital, and drive long-term development.

Challenges in Implementation:

- **Geographical Constraints:** Assam's diverse geography, with hilly terrains, flood-prone areas, and remote villages, makes the implementation of infrastructure projects difficult.
- **Bureaucratic Delays:** Issues such as delays in fund disbursement and beneficiary identification have hindered the timely execution of some schemes.

Recommendations and Way Forward:

- **Innovative Approaches:** In flood-prone areas, more innovative solutions like elevated roads and flood-resistant housing designs should be explored.
- **Monitoring Mechanisms:** Strengthening monitoring mechanisms to ensure transparency and timely execution of projects.
- **Awareness Campaigns:** Conducting awareness programs, especially in rural and remote areas, to ensure that beneficiaries are well-informed about available schemes.

Conclusion:

The Pradhan Mantri development schemes have played a key role in transforming Assam's socio-economic landscape, particularly in areas such as rural development, financial inclusion, skill enhancement, and agricultural growth. Despite ongoing challenges like geographical limitations and low

awareness, the overall impact has been largely positive. With a stronger focus on monitoring, innovation, and inclusivity, these schemes can continue driving Assam's development. The government's role is crucial for the effective execution of the PM-DevINE scheme in Assam. By concentrating on strategic planning, financial management, infrastructure development, and fostering public-private partnerships, the government can help accelerate socio-economic progress in the state. Addressing local needs, promoting transparency, and enhancing monitoring mechanisms will further ensure the scheme reaches its full potential, transforming Assam's economy and improving the quality of life for its people. Additionally, society's contribution is vital for the successful implementation of Pradhan Mantri development schemes in Assam. Community involvement helps align the schemes with local requirements, while active participation in monitoring and awareness efforts promotes transparency and accountability. Local organizations, self-help groups, and individuals work alongside the government to expand outreach, facilitate effective implementation, and maximize the benefits of these initiatives for the state's socio-economic growth.

References:

- 1.Ray, Debraj(2002). Development Economics, India: Oxford University Press, Fifth Impression, p. 250.
2. Kareemulla. K, Ramasundaram. P., “Impact of National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme in India on Rural Poverty and Food Security.” Current Agriculture Research Journal, vol.1, May.2013.
- 3.Government of Assam, Department of Rural Development
- 4.Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers' Welfare, PMFBY Reports 2023.
- 5.Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship, PMKVY Data 2023.
- 6.Ministry of Rural Development, PMGSY Annual Reports 2023.
- 7.Research papers on the socio-economic impact of government schemes in Assam

8. Dhar Soma (2014), "Socio-Economic and Demographic status of Assam: A comparative analysis of Assam with India" published in International Journal of Humanities & Social Science Studies (IJHSSS) ISSN: 2349-6959 (Online), ISSN: 2349-6711 (Print) Volume-I, Issue-III, November 2014, Page No. 108-117 Assam, India.
9. Nayak, Purusottam. (2016). Brahmaputra and the Socio-Economic Life of People of Assam. SSRN Electronic Journal. 10.2139/ssrn.2790210.
10. Barot, Pinal (2019) "Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana Scheme- An Emerging Prospect Of Affordable Housing In India", International Conference On Innovative Practices In Business.
11. Khan, Nisar (2019) "Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana: An Assessment From Housing Adequacy Perspective." International Journal Of Research And Analytical Reviews, Vol.6, No.21.
12. Goswami Anirudha, Talukdar Mrinal : Bridging the Gap: Assam's Leap Forward with PM-DevINE, Published in Pratidin Time 25 Aug 2024,
13. <https://www.pratidintime.com/watch-tower/bridging-the-gap-assams-leap-forward-with-pm-devine>).
14. <https://www.nextias.com/ca/current-affairs/13-10-2022/prime-ministers-development-initiative-for-north-east-region-pm-devine>.
15. Radha, K., and J. Francis Mary. "Progress and Prospects of PMAY Scheme in India." International Journal of Analytical and Experimental Modal Analysis, vol. XII, no. I, 2020.
16. <https://pmay-urban.gov.in/uploads/presentations/Assam.pdf>
17. <https://diragri.assam.gov.in/schemes/pradhan-mantri-fasal-bima-yojana-pmfby>.